

Modelling and Parameter Estimation of Propylene Polymerisation Reactor: Industrial Case Study

Jozef Vargan^{1,2}, Karol Ľubušky³, Miroslav Fikar², Abderrazak M. Latifi¹

¹Université de Lorraine, CNRS, LRGP, F-54000, Nancy, France. ²Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Bratislava 81237, Slovakia. ³Slovnaft, a.s., Bratislava 82412, Slovakia.

Abstract

First-principles modelling is a cornerstone of chemical process engineering; however, it is challenging due to the model complexity, parameter uncertainty, and limited data quality. To address these challenges, this work focuses on parameter identification for a first-principles model of an industrial fluidized-bed reactor used in propylene polymerization. A dataset is collected, including reactant and product concentrations, reactor temperature and pressure, production rates, and mass flow rates. Local and global sensitivity analyses are used to quantify the influence of parameters on the reactor's measured outputs, followed by an orthogonality-based estimability analysis to rank the parameters from the most to the least estimable. The set of estimable parameters is then identified, enabling precise predictions of industrial measurements.

Introduction

Modelling and control of polymerization processes in fluidized-bed reactors, such as those used for polypropylene production, pose significant challenges for process control engineers [1-2]. Specific attention is frequently devoted to predicting molecular weight distribution (MWD). The deconvolution of MWD [3], based on Flory's most probable distribution, has been widely used recently to estimate polymerization kinetic parameters for each type of catalytic site. An enhanced recursive integral matching estimation (RIME) algorithm was developed by [4], which improves information exchange among population particles by employing selective evolutionary crossover and Gaussian random walk strategies, thereby promoting more effective particle evolution and increasing the likelihood of identifying an optimal solution. However, few literature works have been devoted to systematic approaches to identifying polymerization model parameters. Therefore, this study focuses on parameter estimability analysis and on the identification of estimable parameters to improve predictions of polymer production rates, density, and melt flow index at the industrial level.

Process Modelling

An isothermal reactor is considered, in which propylene homopolymerization occurs in the presence of hydrogen and nitrogen. The exothermic reaction is driven by a Ziegler-Natta catalyst consisting of TiCl_3 and an aluminium co-catalyst TEAL ($\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$). The isotactic polymer, which is polypropylene, is produced continuously in the form of granules. The reactor is cylindrical, with a spherical extension at the top of the column where the gaseous polymerisation mixture is discharged into the cooling section (recycled gas) for cooling, while part of the gas is removed for further processing (bleeding). In the cooling section, no chemical reaction occurs. The cooled gas mixture, consisting of C_3H_6 , H_2 , and N_2 is fed to the bottom of the reactor, below the distribution plate. Fresh feed, consisting of several streams, includes propylene, hydrogen, nitrogen, Ziegler-Natta catalyst, and donors of active sites. The temperature of these feeds is assumed to be similar to the reactor temperature, with slightly higher pressure (to feed the plant). Polypropylene is discharged at the bottom of the reactor, above the distribution plate.

A fluidized-bed reactor with a constant-bubble-size model is developed. It consists of a set of differential-algebraic equations (DAEs) describing heat and mass balances, reaction kinetics and thermodynamics, and hydrodynamic models. In addition, the method of moments is used to compute the moments of the chain length distributions for live and dead polymer chains. The resulting model allows the computation of some key polymer properties, including weight- and number-average molecular weights, melt flow index, and density.

Estimability Analysis

Not all model parameters can be estimated from the available measurements. An estimability analysis is used to rank the parameters from the most to the least estimable. It is based on two approaches:

- Local sensitivity analysis, where the dynamics and the new steady state of the model are analyzed following the perturbation of a single parameter of θ .
- Global sensitivity analysis, where the dynamics and the new steady-state of the model are analyzed following multiple perturbations of all parameters of θ . One of the most accurate global sensitivity analysis techniques is the computation of Sobol's sensitivity indices.

In both approaches, the sensitivity matrices are constructed and used to rank the parameters θ , from the most to the least estimable, using an orthogonalization algorithm.

Parameter Identification

The resulting estimable parameters are identified based on the nonlinear least-squares method as follows:

$$\min_p \sum_{t=1}^{\varphi} \|\mathbf{y}(t) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \boldsymbol{\theta})\|_2,$$

where $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_p} \subset \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_\theta}$ is the vector of estimable parameters, a subset of the model parameters. Variables $\mathbf{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y}$ and $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \boldsymbol{\theta}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_y}$ represent vectors of process measurements and model output predictions at each time point $t = 1, \dots, \varphi$, where $\mathbf{x}(t)$ is the vector of model states.

Results

Estimability analysis was applied to 59 parameters, and both local and global analyses showed that only 8 parameters are estimable. They are then identified from a sample of 1000 measurements (training data) with a sampling period of 60 seconds, where the measured outputs consist of concentrations of C_3H_6 , H_2 , and N_2 , bed temperature T_e , melt flow index, production rate, and polypropylene density. The data were filtered using a Savitzky-Golay filter (polynomial order 3 and frame length 9 min) and standardized to a zero initial value and unit standard deviation. To find the global optimum, a multi-start optimization procedure was implemented.

Figure 1. Comparison of measurements and data predictions.

The results are shown in Figure 1, where predictions of propylene, hydrogen, and nitrogen concentrations, and reactor temperature, are compared with measurements (test data). The dynamics of both curves are identical for all variables, both in regions of constant temperature and during transitions between different operating points.

Conclusion

This work focuses on developing a model for an industrial propylene homopolymerization reactor to accurately predict polypropylene properties. The model parameters undergo an estimability analysis, which determines the set of estimable parameters based on the available measurements. To identify the estimable parameters, the model's predicted outputs are compared with industrial data on concentrations, temperature, production rate, polymer density, and melt flow index. The results show that the model predictions correctly match the measured data.

References

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